

A NEW STRUCTURAL MODEL OF ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOR INFLUENCED BY PERSONALITY FACTORS

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Abstract

Purpose – The consequences of the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic on young adults in terms of traits personality with changes in organizational behavior are the main concern of the present paper.

Methodology/approach - The authors invited students to participate in an on-line questionnaires - The Big Five Inventory and conflict questionnaire. Descriptive statistical analysis of observed data, testing research hypotheses, development of a model for organizational behavior, analysis of the connection between organizational behavior and personality traits using a Structural Equation Model (SEM).

Findings – Applying a quantitative research based on BFI questionnaire; the use of a statistical methodology for the evaluation of personality traits within organizational behavior; implementation of the SEM; proposals for solutions to improve organizational behavior.

Research limitations/implications – the proposed structural model is specific only to the analyzed group of respondents, but the methodology used has a pronounced character of generality.

Practical implications – the applicability of the research is found in the developed methodology, and in the understanding of the relationships between personality factors and the moderator effect of young adults.

Originality/value – The research proposes a quantitative statistical methodology for evaluating the personality factors of young adults in the post-pandemic period. The results are compared with the ante pandemic ones.

Key words: Organizational behaviour, Structural model, Statistical analysis

Introduction

The Model of the Five Factors was discovered empirically by Tupes and Christal (1961) by revisiting Cattell's data comprising sets of bipolar adjectives. The five main factors identified were Extroversion, Conscientiousness, Emotional Stability, Agreeableness and Culture (Intellect/Openness). Initially, the structure of personality types is person-centered, later it is expressed through personality dimensions (Isler et al., 2017).

Costa and McCrae (1994) present the five factors as fundamental psychic dispositions with biological bases, indirectly observable and can provide explanations for characteristic psychic adaptations. Psychic adaptations are acquired and include habits, attitudes, skills, values or reasons:

- ✓ extroversion – represents the tendency of the individual to be assertive, active, and in search of emotions, getting involved in the activities of the outside world (Watson and Clark, 1997). Its main dimensions are: affectivity, sociability, assertiveness, level of activism, search for positive sensations and emotions (Goldberg et al., 2005);
- ✓ conformism – highlights the personal characteristics that stimulate and incorporate social cooperation and harmony; considers six dimensions, namely: trust, morality, altruism, cooperation, modesty and compassion (Goldberg et al., 2005);
- ✓ neurosis – describes the tendency to have negative emotional experiences (McCrae and Costa, 1991); it relates to the following six dimensions: anxiety, anger, depression, shyness, insatiability and vulnerability (Goldberg et al., 2005);

- ✓ conscientiousness – reflects the individual's ability to become aware of, control, regulate and direct impulses (Barrick and Mount, 1991); its main dimensions are: personal efficiency, organization, moral rigidity, the need for achievement, self-discipline and prudence (Goldberg et al., 2005);
- ✓ openness to experience represents the tendency of individuals to be imaginative, creative, perceptive and caring; it considers the following dimensions: imagination, artistic interest, affectivity, adventurous spirit, intellect and liberalism (Goldberg et al., 2005).

The worldwide situation in a post – COVID 19 era changed the organizational behaviour of people. The consequences of behaviour, especially related to emotional reactions such as fear, anger, and lack of concentration during professional work, correlated with a distortion of perception. The lack of socialization will change individuals' perspectives regarding their own lives. The studies developed in the last period indicate possible changes in personality traits: individuals with high scores in conscientiousness and agreeableness usually tend to be more conformed to rules asked by the public institutions. Social distancing was more applied by people having high conscientiousness, openness to experience, agreeableness, and low extraversion (Blagov, 2020; Carvalho et al., 2020; Chan et al., 2020). Individuals involved in social cases have high scores for agreeableness and openness (Habashi et al., 2016), but negative thoughts and rumination were observed in those with an important score for neuroticism (Caci et al., 2020; Kroencke et al., 2020).

Organization of research

The authors of the study used statistical methods to identify changes in organizational behaviour based on the BIF personality traits questionnaire applied to young adults.

The research methodology includes the following steps:

1. Definition of the study problem. The problem of the current research is the analysis of the moderating behaviour of the respondent in a conflict situation related to the factors of his behaviour.
2. Choice of questionnaires. Two professional questionnaires were chosen - one for personality factors (BIG5) and another for the moderator character of the young adult in relation to the conflict within the organization.

The instrument used to develop the research was the BFI with five dimensions: extraversion, conscientiousness, agreeableness, neuroticism, and openness. It contains 44 items. The instrument was developed by John, O. P., Donahue, E. M., & Kentle, R. L. (1991). The questionnaire uses a Likert scale: 0:strongly disagree; 1: disagree; 2: neutral; 3: agree; 4: strongly agree.

The questionnaire "Identifying the preferred approach to conflict" was processed and adapted after D.A. Whetten, K.S. Cameron and contains 20 items grouped on five dimensions, as follows: forcing (items: 1, 6, 11, 16), withdrawing/avoiding (items: 4, 9, 14, 19), settling (items: 2, 7, 12, 17), confrontation (items: 5, 10, 15, 20) and compromise (items: 3, 8, 13, 18). The questionnaire uses a Likert scale: 0 - strongly disagree, 1 - disagree, 2 - neutral, 3 - agree, 4 - strongly agree.

3. Choosing the sample of respondents. Young adults form the target population of the study. The sample is considered uniform weight. The participants are 60 students enrolled at "Gheorghe Asachi" Technical University of Iași, Romania, from the Faculty of Industrial Design and Business Management, study program: Engineering and Management. The students were invited to participate in an online questionnaire. Students who expressed interest were provided with a link to complete the questionnaire. The questionnaire using Google Forms was administered in May-June 2022, during the post-COVID-19 pandemic period. Informed consent was obtained virtually on the first page of the online survey. Participation in the study was voluntary, and participants did not receive any compensation. The participants were informed regarding the questionnaire contents and the scale and they were encouraged to use the feedback in case of misunderstands.
4. Descriptive statistical analysis of the two questionnaires, Validation tests of the questionnaire scale, testing the normality of the value series, and analysis of the parameters of the central tendency of the studied variables (Subudhi, 2021).

5. Creation of a structural model for the two scores – personality and moderation. Two structural models have been proposed, one reflective and the other formative, to analyse the relationship between personality and moderator character. The modelling environment is SmartPLS 3.0 (Sayginer, 2020).

Experimental results

The questionnaire for the analysis of the moderating factor includes 20 aspects revealed in table 1.

Table 1. Questionnaire for measuring the moderator level within an organization

Item	Description
1	I defend my position tenaciously
2	I tend to put the needs of others before my own
3	I want to reach an acceptable compromise for both parties
4	I try not to get involved in conflicts
5	I analyse in the smallest details, together with the other party in the conflict, all the issues under discussion
6	I try to find a breach, a weak point in the position of the other.
7	I support harmony in discussions
8	I'm working hard to get at least a part of what I set out to do
9	I avoid open discussion of controversial issues
10	In resolving disagreements, I openly share the information I have with the other parties
11	I like to always win the cause
12	I usually follow the suggestions of others
13	I am looking for a middle way to resolve conflicts
14	I keep to myself what I really believe out of the desire to avoid the resentment of the other
15	I encourage the open sharing of feelings and issues that concern me in discussions
16	I don't like to admit that I was wrong
17	I try not to put the other person in an embarrassing situation
18	I emphasize the advantages that would result from an agreement in which each of us would give up something
19	I encourage others to take the lead in resolving the conflict
20	I state my position only as a point of view.

The coefficient AlphaC=0,361 is calculated. The questionnaire does not have consistency for statistical analysis. It can be seen that there are five inverted items 6, 9, 11, 14, 16. After inverting the variables corresponding to these items, the alphaC score becomes 0,603, a value considered acceptable for statistical analysis (Ravinder, 2020).

A descriptive analysis of the variable that measures the moderator level of the members within the organization in a state of conflict was made.

$$m\text{oderator} = \sum_{i=1}^{20} \text{item}_i$$

Table 2. Moderator variable - statistical parameters

Parameters	Statistic	Std. Error
Mean	55,7667	,83914
Median	56,0000	
Std. Deviation	6,49998	
Minimum	42,00	
Maximum	69,00	
Skewness	,075	,309
Kurtosis	-,981	,608

Table 3. The K-S test for the distribution of the Moderator variable

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.
Moderator	,102	60	,196

The Moderator variable is normally distributed according to the K-S test (table 3). From this descriptive statistic, one can deduce a character of assertive mediator of the respondents, normal for young adults in defining the formation of their characters. The average value $m=55,77$ is representative of the group of respondents. The maximum value that could be reached is 80, and the minimum value is 0. Assertiveness is the optimal mode of solving and reporting to a state of conflict.

Validation of the consistency of the questionnaire for personality factors - the alphaC coefficient is 0,681, a value that represents a normal level of confidence in this questionnaire.

The structural model for the personality factor is made in the SmartPLC 3.0 environment, which has the advantage that it can be applied to variables that do not necessarily have a normal distribution (all the variables attached to the 44 items have a distribution different from the normal distribution). The proposed model is a reflexive one, which means that the dimensions are reflected in the items of the questionnaire (figure 1).

Fig.1 SEM for personality factor

This model contains the most important factors that influence the personality factor of the respondents.

The model is analyzed from the point of view of consistency - reliability (confidence level), and validity (table 4). All the values corresponding to the coefficient alphaC are $\geq 0,699$, and the mean of the variant is close to the value 0,5. According to these values, the proposed structural model is consistent.

Table 4. Validation of the SEM for personality factor

	Cronbach's Alpha	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Agreeableness	0,780	0,476
Conscientiousness	0,699	0,483
Extroversion	0,820	0,548
Neurosis	0,749	0,489
Openness	0,836	0,424
Personality factor	0,845	0,469

Fig. 2 Path coefficient for SEM of personality construct

It is observed that within the construct for the personality score, the four dimensions - agreeableness, conscientiousness, extroversion, openness enter with positive, approximately equal weighting coefficients, and the neurosis dimension influences the personality score inversely proportionally (figure 2).

The results obtained through this structural model conform with empirical logic and do not contradict axiomatically valid natural laws.

The personality-moderator model - is a formative model, each of the two calculated (latent) variables being the result of summing the values of all the important aspects that determine them (figure 3).

The proposed model is not supported by natural logic; it proposes an inverse correlation between the personality factor and the respondent's typology when solving conflict situations in the organizational environment.

To see where this construction comes from, we did an analysis at the level of each dimension of the personality factor related to the moderator score. Thus, all the cause-effect relationships between all the dimensions that characterize the personality and moderator character of the respondents are analyzed. The relationship between agreeableness and the moderating character is positive (0,791) (figure 4). It is a normal relationship.

Fig. 3 The personality-moderator model

Fig. 4 The relationship between agreeableness and the moderating effect

The relationship between conscientiousness and the moderating character is positive 0,742 (figure 5).

Fig. 5. The relationship between conscientiousness and the moderating effect

The relationship between openness and the moderating character is negative -0,751 (figure 6). This relationship is interesting in its logic. He says that a character that is too open negatively influences the mediator status and the involvement in a conflictual state of the individual in an organizational environment. This relationship surprises in the first phase, but a too open position is not recommended in solving a conflict situation.

Fig. 6. The relationship between openness and the moderating character

The relationship between extroversion and the moderating character is positive, 0,704 (figure 7).

Fig.7 The relationship between extroversion and the moderating character

The relationship between neuroticism and the moderating character is negative (-0,702) (figure 8).

Fig.8 The relationship between neuroticism and the moderating character

Corroborated, all the domains that form the personality structure are in a negative correlation with the moderate character of the respondent.

Discussions and conclusions

The current research creates three structural models for the personality factor, the moderating factor and the relationship between the two factors. If the first two models analyzed independently are in accordance with natural logic, the structural model for the causal relationship between the personality construct and the moderating factor is contrary to this natural logic - direct proportionality. This is analyzed in the continuation of the research, and within the personality construct finds a new dimension with an inversely proportional relationship with the moderator effect – openness, in addition to the neurosis dimension.

The results of this analysis can be considered normal, unaffected by the two years of the pandemic. The explanation is that the answers are given by the students of years 1 and 2 who were protected within their families.

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